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Review Article

**THE INCIDENCE OF CO-MORBIDITIES RELATED TO
OBESITY: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW STUDY**¹Dr. Ammad Javaid Chaudhary, ²Dr. Saad Javaid, ³Dr. Shanzay Amin¹King Edward Medical University Lahore, Pakistan., ²Nishtar Medical University Multan, Pakistan., ³Foundation University Medical College.**Article Received:** April 2019**Accepted:** May 2019**Published:** June 2019**Abstract:**

Background: Obesity can increase the risk of a number of medical conditions which can lead to further morbidity and mortality. The purpose of this study is to find out the incidence of each co-morbidity related to obesity and overweight.

Methods: A literature search for the twenty co-morbidities identified in a preliminary search was conducted in Medline and Embase. Studies added that met our inclusion criteria (prospective cohort studies of sufficient size reporting risk estimate based on the incidence of disease) were extracted.

Results: total 89 studies were identified. Only 18 comorbidities which met the inclusion criteria were found. This review found statistically significant associations for obesity with the incidence of type II diabetes, all cancers except esophageal (female), pancreatic and prostate cancer, all cardiovascular diseases (except congestive heart failure), asthma, gallbladder disease, osteoarthritis and chronic back pain. The strongest association between overweight defined by body mass index (BMI) and the incidence of type II diabetes in females were noticed. Statistically significant associations with obesity were found with the incidence of type II diabetes, all cancers except esophageal and prostate cancer, all cardiovascular diseases, asthma, gallbladder disease, osteoarthritis and chronic back pain.

Conclusion: Both overweight and obesity are associated with the incidence of multiple comorbidities including type II diabetes, cancer and cardiovascular diseases.

Key words: obesity, comorbidity, overweight diseases.

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INTRODUCTION:

Previous literature has found that overweight and obesity are major causes of co-morbidities which can lead to further morbidity and mortality [1-3]. As the number of associated co-morbidities continues to increase. Obesity is clearly associated with higher blood pressure, higher fasting insulin, adverse lipid profile and abnormal glucose tolerance tests, which are usually all asymptomatic at adolescence age and detected only opportunistically or via surveillance. Obesity is believed to cause a range of more overt physical problems, with a recent systematic review citing symptoms such as heat intolerance, excessive sweating, intertrigo, heat rash, tiredness, shortness of breath on exercise, joint pain and headaches. [4] Asthma has been weakly related to overweight/obesity in some people., particularly those in which asthma is self-reported or clinically treated rather than more objectively assessed via lung function testing.

To find out the incidence of co-morbidities related to obesity and overweight was the primary objective of this study. Number of recent systematic reviews and meta-analyses were identified on type II diabetes [6], cardiovascular diseases [8,9], cancer [10], breast cancer [11], esophageal or cardiac adenocarcinoma [12], pancreatic cancer [14] and prostate cancer [13].

Secondly, associating the incidence of co-morbidities with overweight and obesity can be done in many ways since there are many different definitions. For instance, many previous literature have combined studies that have found the association with per unit change of BMI (kg/m²) and WC (cm) measurements.

METHOD:**Search strategy:**

A literature search was conducted using the search terms: 'Incidence, Prevalence, Risk, Risk Factors, Cohort Studies, Longitudinal Studies, Follow-up Studies, or Prospective Studies' in combination with 'Adipose Tissue, Obesity, Body Mass Index, or Body Composition. These same search terms were applied to each co-morbidity for both Medline and Embase search engines to retrieve all potentially relevant English articles. We also searched ISI Web of Science, Google Scholar, and the bibliographies of retrieved articles. (Fig 1)

Inclusion criteria:

Prospective cohort study of the general population, relevant outcomes, a sample size of at least 200 subjects, and risk estimate based on the incidence of disease instead of the mortality rate of disease. There were many large cohorts' articles that met our inclusion criteria but the most recent or most authentic information were selected.

Exclusion criteria:

Studies were excluded if they did not provide enough data to allow calculation of unadjusted relative risks (RRs) with 95% confidence intervals (CI) for the overweight and obese groups compared to the normal group.

Data extraction:

Data extracted for study characteristics included study design, country, cohort name, duration of follow-up, number of patients in each study group, age range, gender and ethnicity.

Fig 1: Flowchart of article distribution for all diseases.**RESULT:**

89 relevant and recent studies were identified; many studies featured for more than one co-morbidities. Of the 20 co-morbidities, 18 were identified to have at least one study meeting the inclusion criteria. Some studies were applicable to more than one co-morbidity. No studies were found for dyslipidemia and sleep apnea. The total numbers of studies included for each co-morbidity varied from 1 to 14. Reasons for exclusion are given in Table 1. However, only a small number of studies reported sample ethnicity and of those, the majority was US studies. Among those US studies, one study (endometrial cancer) was about the black women while for the remaining US studies, the proportion of whites ranged from 81% to 95%. Mean of duration follow-

up was 12.5 (SD = 7.2) years. Over half of the studies (53%) were longer than 10 years while less than 10% of the studies were shorter than 5 years. BMI and WC measurements were clinically measured on 43% of the studies and were self-reported on 56% of the studies while one study did not provide such information. Regarding the ascertainment of cases, 43 (48%) studies identified cases from registry, database Centre or clinical evaluation; 34 (38%) studies were based on subject self-reported information with some kind of confirmation method such as medical records review; 6 studies were based on medical records review and 5 studies (4 for asthma and 1 for type-2 diabetes) were relying on self-reported information alone. Note that cancer cases were identified from cancer registry/database on 66% of the studies.

Table 1: Article distribution for all diseases

Diseases	A	B	B (i)	B (ii)	B (iii)	B (iv)	B (v)	B (vi)	B (vii)	C	D	D (i)	D (ii)	D (iii)	E	F	F (i)	F (ii)	G
Type II Diabetes	8142	8075	6687	18	1216	20	28	18	88	67	37	17	6	14	30	21	19	2	9
Colorectal cancer	445	413	5	22	261	8	42	57	18	32	6	2	2	2	26	14	14	0	12
Kidney cancer	2661	2606	55	12	2010	51	50	127	301	55	43	16	18	9	12	7	7	0	5
Prostate cancer	491	462	28	1	258	0	37	52	86	29	14	5	9	0	15	7	6	1	8
Breast cancer	2755	2682	145	18	1793	19	110	195	402	73	43	6	34	3	30	16	13	3	14
Ovarian cancer	241	228	23	1	143	0	10	13	38	13	4	1	3	0	9	0	0	0	9
Endometrial cancer	1249	1192	103	17	729	8	30	105	200	57	41	27	3	11	16	6	5	1	10
Pancreatic cancer	155	131	5	0	81	0	14	7	24	24	15	5	10	0	9	3	2	1	6
Esophageal cancer	230	222	23	0	103	2	13	34	47	8	6	4	2	0	2	1	1	0	1
Hypertension	2882	2773	59	55	2256	53	78	81	191	109	88	23	53	12	21	17	17	0	4
CAD	3041	2966	96	17	2202	42	66	82	461	75	50	10	27	13	25	14	11	3	11
CHF	625	586	10	5	418	6	1	41	105	39	25	0	14	11	14	10	9	1	4
PE	527	497	48	13	321	1	0	24	90	30	11	3	3	5	19	18	18	0	1
Stroke	2783	2755	172	29	1747	17	24	234	532	28	17	6	5	6	11	4	4	0	7
Asthma	1408	1359	89	13	598	47	47	84	481	49	36	2	25	9	13	9	9	0	4
GD	319	305	29	9	175	0	7	32	53	14	5	0	2	3	9	5	5	0	4
OA	853	824	43	10	390	51	38	123	169	29	14	5	2	7	15	12	12	0	3
CBP	324	306	30	20	143	39	11	24	39	18	6	0	4	2	12	11	11	0	1

Potential publication bias was assessed for post-menopausal breast cancer, endometrial cancer, ovarian cancer, colorectal cancer, pancreatic cancer for females and prostate cancer. Some evidence of funnel-plot asymmetry for obesity in prostate cancer were found. Where larger studies tended to show stronger positive association than smaller studies. Evidence of publication bias was not found in the

other meta-analyses. Our sensitivity analyses showed that our results were in general robust with the following exceptions. Associations for both overweight and obesity were slightly weaker in ovarian cancer. Similar country differences were found in pancreatic cancers; in addition, weaker associations were observed in older population. Short follow-up time and of older population showed

slightly weak association of obesity with prostate cancer in many studies. In coronary artery disease for females, studies with shorter follow-up showed weaker associations of both overweight and obese. In coronary artery disease for males, weaker associations were observed in US and Canadian studies. Studies of postmenopausal and senior women on congestive heart failure showed weaker associations for both overweight and obesity.

DISCUSSION:

This study comprehensively reviewed 20 co-morbidities for high quality cohort studies which determine risk factors associated with overweight or obesity. 18 co-morbidities were identified. In Table 2

summary of result can be found. There are many alternative meta-analyses with which we can compare our results. For example, recent meta-analyses have been reported in diabetes, cardiovascular diseases, coronary heart disease, hypertension, cancer, colorectal cancer, gallbladder cancer, pancreatic cancer, ovarian cancer and asthma. Hence, the objective of our study is not only to provide up to date estimates of the risk of all possible co-morbidities attributable to overweight and obesity, but also to do it using consistent definitions and methodology. In assessing whether obesity is related to a given co-morbidity, the occurrence timing of co-morbidities with respect to exposure of obesity is important in determining the causal pathway.

Table 2: Relative co-morbidity risks related to being overweight or obese

Co-morbidity	Measure	Overweight		Obesity	
		Male	Female	Male	Female
Type II Diabetes*	BMI	2.40 (2.12–2.72)	3.92 (3.10–4.97)	6.74 (5.55–8.19)	12.41 (9.03–17.06)
	WC	2.27 (1.67–3.10) [†]	3.40 (2.42–4.78)	5.13 (3.81–6.90) [†]	11.10 (8.23–14.96)
Cancer					
Breast, Postmenopausal	BMI	-	1.08 (1.03–1.14)	-	1.13 (1.05–1.22)
Colorectal	BMI	1.51 (1.37–1.67)	1.45 (1.30–1.62)	1.95 (1.59–2.39)	1.66 (1.52–1.81)
Endometrial	BMI	-	1.53 (1.45–1.61)	-	3.22 (2.91–3.56)
Esophageal	BMI	1.13 (1.02–1.26)	1.15 (0.97–1.36)	1.21 (0.97–1.52)	1.20 (0.95–1.53)
Kidney	BMI	1.40 (1.31–1.49)	1.82 (1.68–1.98)	1.82 (1.61–2.05)	2.64 (2.39–2.90)
Ovarian	BMI	-	1.18 (1.12–1.23)	-	1.28 (1.20–1.36)
Pancreatic	BMI	1.28 (0.94–1.75)	1.24 (0.98–1.56)	2.29 (1.65–3.19)	1.60 (1.17–2.20)
Prostate	BMI	1.14 (1.00–1.31)	-	1.05 (0.85–1.30)	-
Cardiovascular Diseases					
Hypertension*	BMI	1.28 (1.10–1.50)	1.65 (1.24–2.19)	1.84 (1.51–2.24)	2.42 (1.59–3.67)
	WC	NA	1.38 (1.27–1.51)	NA	1.90 (1.77–2.03)

Coronary Artery Disease*	BMI	1.29 (1.18–1.41) [†]	1.80 (1.64–1.98)	1.72 (1.51–1.96) [†]	3.10 (2.81–3.43)
	WC	1.41 (1.16–1.72) [†]	1.82 (1.41–2.36)	1.81 (1.45–2.25) [†]	2.69 (2.05–3.53)
Congestive Heart Failure*	BMI	1.31 (0.96–1.79)	1.27 (0.68–2.37) [†]	1.79 (1.24–2.59)	1.78 (1.07–2.95) [†]
Pulmonary Embolism	BMI	1.91 (1.39–2.64)	1.91 (1.39–2.64)	3.51 (2.61–4.73)	3.51 (2.61–4.73)
Stroke*	BMI	1.23 (1.13–1.34) [†]	1.15 (1.00–1.32) [†]	1.51 (1.33–1.72) [†]	1.49 (1.27–1.74) [†]
Other					
Asthma	BMI	1.20 (1.08–1.33) [†]	1.25 (1.05–1.49) [†]	1.43 (1.14–1.79) [†]	1.78 (1.36–2.32) [†]
Gallbladder Disease*	BMI	1.09 (0.87–1.37) [‡]	1.44 (1.05–1.98) [‡]	1.43 (1.04–1.96) [‡]	2.32 (1.17–4.57) [‡]
	WC	1.61 (1.40–1.85) [†]	NA	2.38 (2.06–2.75) [†]	NA
Osteoarthritis	BMI	2.76 (2.05–3.70)	1.80 (1.75–1.85) [†]	4.20 (2.76–6.41)	1.96 (1.88–2.04) [†]
Chronic Back Pain	BMI	1.59 (1.34–1.89) [†]	1.59 (1.34–1.89) [†]	2.81 (2.27–3.48) [†]	2.81 (2.27–3.48) [†]

CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, this study provides a comprehensive estimate of the incidence of 18 co-morbidities attributable to overweight and obesity using standardized and consistent definitions and methodologies. Our findings confirm that overweight and obesity carry a profound health burden and will have a significant impact on health expenditures.

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